

From The Desk of Guest Editor....

Periodontology in Multidisciplinary Approach: Bridging The Gaps in Oral Health

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Evidence-based periodontology has made us understand that most patients having various dental or medical treatments require a multidisciplinary rather than a personalised dental treatment approach. The intercommunication and liaison between periodontology and endodontics, prosthodontics, implant dentistry, orthodontics, oral pathology, Aesthetic dentistry, oral & maxillofacial surgery, and paediatric dentistry need to be discussed. In this, a conscious effort has been made to touch upon various fields of dental science and its relationship with periodontology.

Understanding these inter-relationships can improve the clinician's ability to establish the correct diagnosis, evaluate the prognosis of the affected tooth or teeth, and design and carry out the appropriate treatment according to biological and clinical evidences.

Inter-relationships Between Endodontics & Periodontology

The pulp periodontal relationship is distinct and is regarded as a single continuous system or a biological entity with numerous communication channels. The therapy and prognosis of Endo-Perio Lesions depend heavily on accurate diagnosis.

The degree of the periodontal lesion and the pulp vitality should be taken into account while planning the treatment. If adequate irrigation protocol is followed during cleaning and shaping and they recover with proper endodontic therapy, the prognosis of the primary endodontic lesion is typically good. Only periodontal therapy can be used to treat primary periodontal lesions.

A patient that calls for endodontic and periodontal regeneration treatment, is true mixed lesions. True combined endo-perio lesion should initially be treated endodontically before other etiological factors, like as periodontal care, are addressed. Endo-perio lesions pose a risk to dentists since a comprehensive approach is necessary to get a good outcome.

The Impact of Prosthetic Factors On Periodontal / Peri-implant Health

Prosthodontists should properly design the prosthesis in consonance with the surrounding periodontium for long-term maintenance of periodontal / peri-implant health. Faulty restorations tend to accumulate plaque and food debris, thereby increasing periodontal disease progression. Violation of biologic width also results in periodontal inflammation.

An interdisciplinary approach requiring coordinated efforts by the prosthodontist and periodontist is the need of an hour. Close attention should be paid to both soft and hard tissues around teeth and implants before, during and after restorative procedures to produce a successful outcome. It also gives the patient the benefit of comprehensive treatment with precise and long-lasting restorations.

Ortho-perio Synergy

A failure to recognise periodontal susceptibility can destroy a magnificent orthodontic treatment. The interrelationship between orthodontics and periodontics often resembles symbiosis. In many cases, periodontal health is improved by orthodontic tooth movement, whereas orthodontic tooth movement is often facilitated by periodontal therapy.

Periodontal disease is not necessarily a contraindication to orthodontic treatment provided that the condition has already been stabilised, however, loss of alveolar bone and soft tissue architecture may pose considerable challenges to oral rehabilitation.

Pediatric Dentistry And Periodontic Interface

Child oral health mostly emphasises dental caries and is segregated from general healthcare. So, it has become very crucial to realise the condition of oral tissue and mainly the periodontium in health and disease to facilitate long-lasting oral health in youth.

Regular screening (periodontal screening and recording) is advised for children and young teens with deciduous and mixed dentition. Such screening helps to find prior signs and symptoms of periodontal tissue destruction. Paediatric dentistry and periodontology should work cohesively to come up with proof, capability and endorsements to ensure that all health professionals will be able to recognise the oral health problems of children.

The Nexus Between Periodontology And Oral Pathology

The gingiva and buccal mucosa are associated with numerous local and systemic diseases. There are certain rare pathologies that may manifest in soft or hard tissue components of periodontium that can be deliberated by periodontists.

Periodontists and oral pathologists should work together to ensure that these lesions are diagnosed and managed in a timely manner. Lesions of the periodontium may be of a simple local nature or may be an indication of severe local or systemic disease. The patients with such lesions will be referred to periodontists, who will need to have a structured plan to follow when signs and/or symptoms of gingival pathology persist.

Radiology In Periodontology

Periodontal examination remains incomplete without accurate radiographs, which play an important role in the assessment of periodontal disease. An overall assessment of periodontal tissues is made on the basis of both the clinical examination and radiographic findings.

Two-dimensional periapical and panoramic radiographs are routinely used for diagnosing periodontal bone levels. In two-dimensional imaging, evaluation of bone craters, lamina dura and periodontal bone level is limited by projection geometry and superpositions of adjacent anatomical structures. Those limitations of 2D radiographs can be eliminated by three-dimensional imaging techniques such as computed tomography. Cone beam computed tomography (CBCT) generates 3D volumetric images and is also commonly used in dentistry.

Despite its limitations, periodontal examination is incomplete without accurate radiographs, which can show most bony changes in association with periodontal disease, CBCT applications provide obvious benefits in periodontology, although it should be used when two-dimensional radiographs are insufficient considering the necessity and the potential radiation hazards of the examination

Conclusion

The interdisciplinary approach in periodontology includes a structured collaboration between periodontists and other specialities involved in patient treatment. There are multiple treatment plans that will provide both clinical predictability and patient satisfaction in achieving a higher level of success.

The interdisciplinary approach develops a classic relationship within various specialities of dentistry that should go hand in hand with the complete well-being of the patient. The preservation and maintenance of the natural dentition in health is of prime importance in an integral interdisciplinary approach to periodontal care.

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